

D8.3 Dedicated project page on the beneficiaries' websites

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Deliverable Information Sheet

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Executive summary

This deliverable contains the specific pages created by every LIFE PRISTINE partner on their respective corporate websites. Access to each of these pages is provided.

[NOTE: Front page and Executive summary will be published in the website for all deliverables]

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1 Overall principles

In order to increase the visibility of LIFE PRISTINE, each partner must create a dedicated page on their respective website with a short summary of the project and its objectives.

All of the pages have to provide access to the LIFE PRISTINE website, embedded in EUT's site.

2 Dedicated page in each partner's website

2.1 ACCIONA

[Link](#)

INCREASING PROJECTS' SUSTAINABILITY

The LIFE PRISTINE project aims to develop an integrated solution to remove different contaminants of emerging concern from water. These substances, of different origin, chemical nature and generated by anthropogenic action, are a matter of growing concern due to the effects that their presence in the environment may cause on human and ecological health. The use of most of these substances is not yet regulated, partially because their presence is limited to very low concentrations that take current techniques to the limit of detection, making it difficult to take adequate measures to protect human health and the ecosystems.

LIFE PRISTINE, focuses on removing emerging contaminants such as PFAS, pesticides, pharmaceuticals, toxins, antibiotic resistance genes, and microplastics, in drinking and wastewater. For this, the project proposes a solution that integrates different technologies, including adsorption processes, membrane filtration, advanced oxidation processes and artificial intelligence tools, in order to eliminate at least 80% of contaminants of emerging concern in wastewater and drinking water, with a 30% operational improvement.

The LIFE PRISTINE project, coordinated by ACCIONA, is supported by the European Union through the LIFE Funding Program for the environment and climate action, and count on the participation of EURECAT, NX Filtration, Xylem Services and the Regional Entity for Wastewater Sanitation and Treatment in Murcia (ESAMUR), in addition to the support of the Bilbao Bizkaia Water Consortium (CABB). The project started in August 2022 and will last for 4 years.

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2.2 Eurecat

[LIFE PRISTINE official website](#) is embedded in Eurecat webpage.

2.3 NX Filtration

[Link](#)

Enschede, the Netherlands, 11 October 2022

NX Filtration part of ACCIONA-led initiative to eliminate emerging pollutants from water sources

NX Filtration, the global provider of breakthrough direct nanofiltration technology for pure and affordable water, announces its participation in the European innovation project LIFE PRISTINE, led by ACCIONA S.A. The project's objective is to eliminate emerging contaminants in the integral water cycle, one of the essential measures to promote alternative water resources in the face of water scarcity, which affects more than 2.8 billion people worldwide.

- The LIFE PRISTINE project has a budget of 4 million euros and is coordinated by ACCIONA, the Spanish sustainable infrastructure solutions group. Next to ACCIONA and NX Filtration, project partners include Eurecat, Xylem Services, the Regional Entity for Wastewater Sanitation and Treatment of the Murcia Region (ESAMUR) and the water utility provider Bilbao Bizkaia Water Consortium (CABB).

- The LIFE PRISTINE project combines water treatment processes, including NX Filtration's hollow fiber nanofiltration membranes, with artificial intelligence-based digital tools to develop a solution that removes emerging pollutants in the integrated water cycle. The integrated and versatile PRISTINE solution will be demonstrated in a representative full-scale operational environment.

Many forums have alerted on the urgent need to take steps to protect water resources, mainly through a reduction in water consumption but also by promoting alternative resources and reuse. These new resources are essential to guarantee water supplies for the future. One of the challenges to overcome fostering the reuse of water is the elimination of emerging pollutants and microplastics. These substances of anthropogenic origin are difficult to eliminate by using existing treatment systems and they may end up in seas and rivers, or even enter the food chain. Their presence may create hazards, which is why there is increasing emphasis on regulating the use of these substances and developing solutions to remove them from the environment.

LIFE PRISTINE is a sustainable alternative to ensure the elimination of emerging pollutants (+80%) in the end-to-end water cycle. It goes beyond the limits set by Directive 2020/2184/CE on Water for Human Consumption and the new European Regulation on minimum requirements for water reuse (Regulation (UE) 2020/741). LIFE PRISTINE focuses on emerging pollutants of the PFAS type (Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl substances, used e.g. in flame retardants), pesticides, pharmaceutical and personal care products, toxins microplastics and genes of microorganisms that are resistant to antibiotics. The project will help to strengthen the existing legislation and promote the reuse of water with the highest quality and safety standards.

The PRISTINE solution involves processes of adsorption, nanofiltration and advanced oxidation using virtual sensors, process modelling and decision-making support tools. It will be capable of eliminating emerging pollutants efficiently (+80%, -30% OpEx) from water sources and wastewater effluent. The PRISTINE project will be demonstrated in a representative operating environment on a real scale: treating the secondary effluent of a treatment plant in Murcia and supporting drinking water pre-treatment in the Bilbao Bizkaia Advanced Water Treatment Centre (CATABB).

More about the PRISTINE project

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More information

2.4 ESAMUR

[Link](#)

LIFE PRISTINE

Integrated Solution to remove Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs) from water streams

Inicio: 01/08/2022

Finalizacion: 31/07/2026

Visitar web

Menos información

PRISTINE

The PRISTINE project has received funding from the LIFE Programme of the European Union

The information included in this web portal reflects only the author's view and the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of it

LIFE PRISTINE project aims to develop the PRISTINE Integrated Solution to remove Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs) from water streams.

The PRISTINE Integrated Solution will be adaptable on a case-by-case basis for drinking water (DW), to protect humans from CECs, and for wastewater (WW), to protect the environment and remove these contaminants from the water cycle. In opposition to other existing technologies, the PRISTINE Integrated Solution, will permanently remove CECs from water, thus directly applying Zero Waste and Circular Economy principles and coming ahead of existing and near future CECs regulations. The PRISTINE Integrated Solution is based on the synergistical combination of individual technologies: i) encapsulated adsorbent technology, ii) hollow-fibre NF membrane, and iii) AOP processes (UV-LED combined with ozonation and/or H₂O₂), being these technologies controlled and optimized by a Decision Support System fed by AI-based soft-sensors for the online estimation of CECs concentration levels. LIFE PRISTINE will focus on PFAS, pesticides, PPCPs, toxins, antibiotic resistance genes and microplastics, as main CECs families, designated according previous studies in the two demo sites and existing literature. LIFE PRISTINE goal is to effectively remove >80% of every CECs in WW and DW scenarios, going further if requested by existing legislation.

Furthermore, the PRISTINE Integrated Solution will be costeffective, 30 % lower OpEx cost that comparable technologies. PRISTINE Integrated Solution will be demonstrated in DW and WW representative scenarios during a year each, allowing the technology to reach a TRL7. Dissemination and communication actions of LIFE PRISTINE will prosecute the awareness raising of the public towards the use and fate of CEC, and to be the background and support for new policies and legislations to protect EU citizens and their environment in the near future.

2.5 Xylem

Xylem specific section about the LIFE PRISTINE project will be part of the Xylem's [Innovation Ecosystem](#) page, which reports in a short format about collaborations to drive breakthrough innovation.

The website contribution is in the process of being published and expected to be online before March 2023, with the following layout:

LIFE PRISTINE project

Xylem is a consortium member on the [LIFE PRISTINE project](#), which is working to integrate adsorption, membrane filtration, advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) and artificial intelligence tools to create a cost-effective solution for eliminating contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) in drinking and wastewater. The carried-out work with the project partners ACCIONA, Eurecat, NX Filtration and ESAMUR will demonstrate the potential of UV-LEDs, and the role of Xylem's technology to remove CECs from the water cycle, being the basis for a sustainable future.

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